

Exchange between chestnut growers

Introduction

During INGECA project, a lot of effort was put into dissemination activities, with 8 thematic meetings, 2 seminars and 2 field visits. These activities permitted to chestnut growers to share experiences about the innovations tested (endothermic treatments with *Trichoderma* spp., use of BITE technology, mobile charcoal kiln prototype for local biochar production), to share approaches in chestnut grove management and production as well as to explore specific aspects like grafting, pruning, variety, disease control, in different regions (Tuscany, Lazio and Calabria). The project began in 2020, right at the beginning of the Covid19 pandemic crisis, so it was decided not to conduct remote dissemination activities, but rather to wait for the end of pandemic restrictions.

Lessons learned

Dissemination activities were very useful to engage chestnut growers and to demonstrate the effectiveness of a chestnut grove management that's also economically and environmentally sustainable.

The project started in 2020 exactly at the beginning of the Covid19 pandemic crisis. In order to enhance real knowledge exchange between partners, it was chosen not to do remote dissemination activities but rather to wait until the end of pandemic restrictions. This has favored personal contacts, allowed participants to know important chestnut growing realities on a regional and extra-regional scale and practical demonstrations in the field. The chestnut production sector is facing many difficulties due to environmental, social and economic aspects. These sharing-knowledge activities are fundamental to establishing durable relationships between the multiple actors of the production chain and to build stable networks, capable to operate also after the end of the project.

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Further information

<https://www.psingeca.it/it>

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